

CHITOSAN-BASED ORGANO BentonITES FOR THE SORPTION OF TRANSITION METAL IONS APIS MELLIFERA AND THEIR APPLICATION

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Abstract. The study investigates the processes of metal ion sorption on organobentonites (DB+CH (2), VB+CH (3), PBMB+CH (5)) and organovermiculite (KV+CH (6)), obtained on the basis of *Apis Mellifera* chitosan from vermiculite clays of Tebinbulak (KV), Dekhkanabad (DB), Navoi (VB), and Navbahor (PBMB, PBG, PBG), located in various regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The research examined the dependence of metal sorption on the pH of the medium, the type of organovermiculite, and the type of organosorbent. The processes of sorption and desorption of transition metal ions were studied in detail. The dependence of the static exchange capacity of organosorbents on the pH of the medium was analyzed. The regeneration cycle of the sorbent was found to be of significant importance for the practical application of organosorbents.

Keywords: intermediate metals, local raw materials, bentonite, chitosan, sorption, desorption.

Introduction. Rapid population growth and development of the manufacturing industry in the world annually increase the need for effective treatment of industrial wastewater. As is known, industrial enterprises around the world discharge dyes, heavy metals, organic reagents, surfactants and other chemical compounds into wastewater, the concentration of which often exceeds permissible standards [1–5].

In recent years, due to the growth in the number of industrial enterprises, more and more attention has been paid to the problem of wastewater purification from harmful substances. Although mineral clays are an accessible and effective sorption material, their practical application is limited. The main disadvantages are low specific surface area, difficulties in regeneration and limited sorption capacity. In this regard, studies have shown that wastewater can be effectively purified using biocomposites based on chitosan and mineral clays [6–10].

Materials and methods. To determine the sorption of non-ferrous metal ions from aqueous solutions, artificial solutions were prepared using CuSO₄ and Ni(NO₃)₂ salts. Changes in metal concentrations after sorption were determined spectrophotometrically. A UV 5100 spectrophotometer (Metash, China) was used.

During the studies, changes in the concentration of metal ions in the solution after sorption by synthesized organosorbents were determined using the spectrophotometric method. For this purpose, standard solutions of metal salts with known concentrations were prepared and their absorption spectra were recorded. Measurements were carried out using a UV 5100 spectrophotometer (Metash, China).

When obtaining the spectra, the absorption spectra of Cu²⁺ and Ni²⁺ ions in the form of their complex compounds were used. During the experiments, Cu²⁺ ions in aqueous solutions were determined in the form of a copper-ammonia complex. In order to justify the use of organosorbents

for cleaning waste and process water from copper and nickel ions, a technical mode of sorption under dynamic conditions was developed. For this, the sorbent was placed in a column with a bulk density of 0.2 g / cm³, activated with a 0.1 N NaOH solution and a CuSO₄ solution with a concentration of 0.1 g / l was passed through it.

Results and discussion. The dynamic exchange capacity (DEC) of the sorbent for Cu²⁺ ions was 175 mg/g at pH = 4.2 and reached 330 mg/g at pH = 12. Data analysis showed that the efficiency of copper ion sorption depends on the pH of the medium, which is due to a change in the ionic state of Cu²⁺.

Copper sorption is also observed in an acidic medium (DEC = 175 mg/g at pH = 4.4), which is due to the formation of chelate complexes between copper ions and amino groups on the organosorbent surface.

Taking this into account, a series of studies were conducted to study the dependence of Cu²⁺ and Ni²⁺ ion sorption on the pH of the solution using synthesized organobentonites.

The data obtained indicate the dependence of metal sorption on the pH of the medium, the type of organovermiculite and organosorbent. Sorption of metal ions on organovermiculite and organosorbents increases at pH = 4–5. (Pic.1. a,b,c,d,e,f

Figure 1. Dependence of Cu²⁺ and Ni²⁺ metal sorption of PBMB+XZ, PBG+XZ, PPD+XZ, DB+XZ, VB+XZ organobentonite on pH (C_{Me}=0.1 n, m_{sorb}=0.1 g, τ=2 s, V=10 ml)

According to the results of the study of the sorption of metals by organosorbents, the static exchange capacity (mg-eq/g) of organosorbents in the optimal pH environment is as follows: Ni²⁺ – up to 2.4-2.78, (pH=5); Cu²⁺ - up to 3.21-4.25 (pH=5). We can see that it increases. The degree of sorption of metal ions exceeds the maximum level in the pH range of the solution medium from pH=4 to pH=7. This indicates that the sorption of metal ions in a weakly acidic environment, the formation of acid complexes of various compositions, the formation of ionic associations with protonated active functional groups of the ligand - amino groups.

According to the results of the study of metal sorption, the static exchange capacity of organosorbents in the optimal environment (mg-eq/g) is:

Ni^{2+} – 2.1 (at pH = 5),

Cu^{2+} – 2.5 (at pH = 4).

It has also been established that the degree of sorption of metal ions with an increase in the pH of the solution medium passes through a maximum in the pH range from 2 to 6. With a further increase in pH - from neutral to alkaline medium - the degree of sorption decreases.

This indicates that during the sorption of metal ions in an acidic medium, acidic complexes of various compositions are formed, as well as ionic associations with protonated active functional groups of organosorbents.

Optimum pH values for sorption correspond to the pH values at which acidic complexes of the corresponding metals are formed. Accordingly, the degree of sorption of the studied metal ions on organosorbents increases in the following order: $\text{Ni}^{2+} < \text{Cu}^{2+}$.

Organosorbents contain amino and hydroxy groups, and in a weakly acidic medium, these groups are activated due to protonation. As a result, the sorption of metal ions occurs due to the formation of ionic bonds with activated functional groups on the surface of organosorbents. When the solution passes into an alkaline environment, metal ions precipitate in the organosorbent phase, forming corresponding hydroxides, and in a highly alkaline environment, hydroxocomplexes.

According to the results of the study of metal sorption by organosorbents, the static exchange capacity (mg-eq/g) in the optimal pH environment is:

Ni^{2+} — up to 2.4–2.78 (at pH = 5); Cu^{2+} — up to 3.21–4.25 (at pH = 5).

It is clearly seen that the exchange capacity increases. The degree of metal ion sorption reaches its maximum level in the pH range from 4 to 7. This indicates that in a weakly acidic environment, metal ion sorption is accompanied by the formation of acid complexes of various compositions, as well as ion associations with protonated active functional groups of the ligand — amino groups.

It was found that the sorption time of copper and nickel ions on organosorbents is: Cu^{2+} — 30–45 minutes, Ni^{2+} — 50–60 minutes.

The properties of the studied organosorbents were compared with industrial sorbents. Based on the results obtained, it was found that these organosorbents are not inferior in their characteristics to the widely used foreign sorbents such as BAU-A and KU-2-8, which are effectively used in various industries.

Currently, there are several methods for removing or reducing the concentration of metal ions contained in wastewater. Of particular importance among them is the method of sorption of metal ions using various organosorbents.

Taking this into account, the sorption isotherms of copper and nickel ions were studied based on the Langmuir and Freundlich models. Based on the modeling results, the calculated parameters of the Langmuir isotherms for the sorption of Cu^{2+} ions on organosorbents modified with chitosan were: $q_{\text{max}} = 181.8\text{--}212.7$ mg/g, KL — the corresponding values of the Langmuir coefficient. The values of the Freundlich coefficient KF increased to 3.76–4.04, which indicates an increased sorption capacity of the modified organosorbents. An analysis of the calculated parameters of the kinetic models of pseudo-first and pseudo-second order of Cu^{2+} ions sorption on organosorbents was carried out. When comparing these models, it was found that the calculated value of the pseudo-second-order kinetic parameter for Cu^{2+} ions is $q_e = 153.8\text{--}172.4$ mg/g. Using similar methods, the parameters of the pseudo-first and pseudo-second-order kinetic models for

the sorption of Ni²⁺ ions were calculated. Based on the data on the adsorption process of Cu²⁺ ions on organosorbents, the change in thermodynamic functions was calculated.

The thermodynamic parameters of the process were determined based on the dependence of the equilibrium constant on temperature according to the equation:

$\Delta G = -RT \ln K$. Since $\Delta G = \Delta H - T\Delta S$, the values of ΔH and ΔS were calculated. For this purpose, a graph of the dependence of $\ln K$ on $1/T$ was constructed, and the values of ΔH and ΔS were determined from the slope of the line. With increasing temperature, the maximum value of adsorption by organosorbents increases. In this case, an ambiguous change in the value of the equilibrium constant is observed - in some cases it increases, in others it decreases.

For organosorbents, the values of the thermodynamic parameters were: $\Delta H^0 = 1.95-5.0$ kJ/mol, $\Delta S^0 = 7.97-17.45$ J/(mol K). The change in the equilibrium constant with temperature is due to the fact that the binding of ions occurs not only due to ion transfer, but also due to weak physical interactions. Since such interactions weaken with increasing temperature, this leads to a decrease in the value of the equilibrium constant. Based on the obtained isotherms, it was established that the process of adsorption of Cu²⁺ ions on organosorbents at different temperatures corresponds to the mechanism of monomolecular sorption.

At present, an important indicator for the practical application of organosorbents is the possibility of their repeated use, i.e. the regeneration cycle.

The organosorbent was regenerated using a 0.5 N solution of sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄). It was found that the organosorbent has high chemical stability and retains its sorption properties during repeated use. As shown in the table below, the dynamic exchange capacity (DEC) changed by only 5–10% after 10 sorption-desorption cycles.

For comparison, the processes of sorption-desorption of Ni²⁺ ions were studied in a similar way.

Thus, organovermiculites and organobentonites modified with vermiculite and bentonite based on chitosan can be effectively used to purify wastewater from copper (Cu²⁺) and nickel (Ni²⁺) ions, as well as for concentrating process solutions. The table above shows the results of the study of the effect of the initial concentration of Cu²⁺ ions in the solution on the dynamic exchange capacity (DEC) of the organosorbent, as well as the dependence of the degree of sorption on the flow rate of the solution through the column filled with the organosorbent.

Thus, the sorption capacity of the organosorbent remains high even with an increase in the flow rate of the solution by 3-4 times, which makes it promising for practical use in water treatment systems.

During the sorption process, metal ions exchange with ions of the functional groups of the organosorbent according to the following ion-exchange reaction:

One of the modern analytical methods for studying the sorption of heavy metal ions from aqueous solutions is energy-dispersive spectral analysis (EDSA). Using this method, energy-dispersive spectra of bentonite clays and organosorbents modified on their basis were obtained, based on which the elemental composition of the studied samples was established. When comparing the composition of the original industrial wastewater and samples after passing them through a column with an organosorbent, effective removal of the following metal ions was established: iron (Fe) - 5.2-5.5 mg / l; titanium (Ti) - 4 mg / l; potassium (K) - 2 mg / l; calcium (Ca) - 5.9 mg / l. In addition, even such radioactive elements as cerium (Ce) are sorbed - 4.13 mg

/ l; vanadium - is removed 3.9 times more effectively; nickel - by 0.12%; manganese (Mn) — by 0.27%; sulfur (S) — up to 0.18%.

Theoretically, depending on the concentration of metals in the desorbed (eluted) solution, elution curves are formed, reflecting the dynamics of the release of metals from the sorbent. To plot such curves, samples were taken from the resulting desorbate at certain time intervals, in which the quantitative content of metals was determined. The desorption process is described by the following reaction:

Conclusion

In conclusion, it should be noted that among the studied organosorbents synthesized on the basis of chitosan, the highest sorption capacity with respect to the radioactive element cerium was possessed by the following samples: DB + Xz (2), VB + Xz (3), PBMB + Xz (5), as well as organovermiculite KV + Xz (6). This allows us to consider these sorbents as an effective alternative to imported materials, with the possibility of their local production and practical application in wastewater treatment systems.

REFERENCES

1. Khademi F., Salehi M.B., Mortaheb H.R., et al. Design and Fabrication of Co([CHITOSAN-AMPS-AA]/PEI-MBA) Nanocomposite Hydrogel as an Effective Solution for Tin and Platinum Ions Removal in Wastewater Treatment: Selective Platinum Reduction // J Polym Environ. – 2024. – P. 10924. – DOI: 10.1007/s10924-024-03356-9.
2. Rahimi S. and Irannajad M., Sulfate Removal from Acid Mine Drainage by Chitosan Modified Red Mud Using Analytical Methods: Isothermal, Kinetic and Thermodynamic Studies. Journal of Environmental Engineering. 2024. Том 150, Выпуск 10. P.7304. DOI:10.1061/JOEEDU.EEENG- 7304.
3. Boceiri N. et.al. Preparation and antibacterial activity of new N-salicylideneaniline organomodified Algerian clays. Applied Clay Science 2023., (246) P.107184.
4. Aliyeva M.T., Xolturayeva N.R., Ikhtiyarova G.A. Obtaining compositions based on local raw materials for textile industrial wastewater treatment. *Австрский журнал технических и естественных наук*. AJTNS. 9-10. 2022. P. 36-40. DOI:/10.29013/AJT-22-9.10-36-40.
5. M. Aliyeva, G.A. Ikhtiyarova, N. R. Xolturayeva, D. Q. Shomurodov, O. A. Geldiyev// Obtaining an organosorbent based on Apis Mellifera chitosan and bentonite and using it in cleaning textile wastewater from dyes and metals. 2024. https://www.e3sconferences.org/articles/e3sconf/abs/2024/27/e3sconf_icecae2024_03051/e3sconf_icecae2024_03051.html
6. E.Egamberdiyev, Kh. Khaydullaev, S. Abdurazzoqova, Q. Khoshimov, O. Muratkulov, Kh. Tilovov, B. Rakhimjonov, M. Alieva // Composite papers based on natural polymers. // 2024. https://www.e3sconferences.org/articles/e3sconf/abs/2024/27/e3sconf_icecae2024_03031/e3sconf_icecae2024_03031.html.
- i. Baxtiyor Shaykulov, Fayzulla Nurkulov, Abdulahat Djalilov/ Investigation of fire-resistant metal coatings/ Science and innovation International Scientific journal 5 may 2023, p. 162-165. (<https://oak.uz/pages/4802>).
7. Aliyeva Mukaddas Tuychiyevna, Ikhtiyarova Gulnora Akmalovna Adsorption of indigo dye from textile wastewater onto chitosan-modified vermiculite. “WOMEN IN STEM”

International festival, Tashkent, February 13 – 15, 2024., PP. 167-168.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10643244>.

8. Ikhtiyarova G.A., Kholturaeva N.R., Alieva M.T. // Synthesis of chitosan complex *Apis Mellifera* with silver and the study of their physico-chemical properties. *Бакы*. P.353-354+
9. Alieva Mukaddas Tuychievna, - Ikhtiyarova Gulnora Akmalovna, Kholturaeva Noroy Ruzmatovna // Modification of mineral clay and the basis of chitosan and its use in wastewater treatment and textile industry. Санкт петербург. VII International Scientific and Practical Conference «EDUCATION AND SCIENCE IN THE 21st CENTURY» in October, 2022 - Научно-исследовательская часть. Invites to participate in VII International Scientific and Practical Conference «EDUCATION AND SCIENCE IN THE 21st CENTURY». 2022. P.12-14.